

Efficient Deep Discriminant Embedding: Application to Face Beauty Prediction and Classification

F. Dornaika, A. Moujahid, K. Wang and X. Feng

University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) and IKERBASQUE, San Sebastian, Spain

Northwestern Polytechnical University (NPU) China and University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), San Sebastian, Spain

Abstract

Inspired by deep learning architectures, we introduce a multi-layer local discriminant embedding algorithm that integrates feature selection as a main step to capture the most relevant and discriminant features of an input face image or face descriptor. The proposed framework allows to transform any linear method to a deep variant via a cascaded feature extraction and selection architecture able to convert weak and noisy descriptors to strong ones. As a case study, the local discriminant embedding (LDE) projection is adopted as a linear feature extraction method. The resulting framework can be considered as an efficient deep discriminant embedding technique. To validate this framework, we have considered two different computer vision problems: face beauty prediction which involves both classification and regression tasks, and face recognition which is a classical classification problem. Experiments conducted on different public benchmark databases show that this approach enhances the performance of the LDE algorithm and provides a discriminating strategy to solve the dimensionality reduction problem. For face beauty regression, our proposed framework achieved on average an improvement of about 5% and 7% with respect to two other configurations where only VGG-face and VGG-face followed by LDE have been considered. For face beauty classification, the proposed algorithm outperformed many classical manifold learning techniques reaching in some databases improvements of about 10%.

Keywords: Manifold learning, feature subset selection, multi-layer architecture, Discriminant embedding, dimensionality reduction, image-based face beauty analysis, classification

Efficient Deep Discriminant Embedding: Application to Face Beauty Prediction and Classification

F. Dornaika, A. Moujahid, K. Wang and X. Feng

University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) and IKERBASQUE, San Sebastian, Spain

Northwestern Polytechnical University (NPU) China and University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), San Sebastian, Spain

1. Introduction

In order to enable image understanding by machines, supervised and semi-supervised techniques have been a main trend in computer vision [1, 2]. In recent times, deep learning paradigm has brought significant progresses to machine learning and artificial intelligence fields. During the last years, the development of deep learning architectures for computer vision applications has been widely witnessed [6, 7, 8].

Deep learning is a sub-field of machine learning dealing with algorithms inspired by the structure and function of the brain. These algorithms are essentially based on artificial neural networks, and are able to automatically extract the patterns that may exist in raw data. As a result, feature extractors which were used to transform the raw data are no longer required. This approach supports the idea that learning models have to go deep in order to tackle complicated learning tasks.

Usually, deep learning term refers to deep artificial neural networks formed by multiple layers of non-linear functions that can be trained by back-propagation. The power and flexibility of deep learning algorithms have recently motivated researchers to extend deep architectures to other machine learning approaches that are not based on neural networks [9, 10].

This work reports a simple deep manifold-learning strategy based on a CNN architecture where the response of a given layer is performed in three steps: First, we project the input data onto a low dimensional space using any given linear feature extraction algorithm. In this work, as a case study, the supervised Local Discriminant Embedding (LDE) [14] algorithm has been

used. Then, we perform a score-based feature selection of the obtained features in order to identify and retain those with the best discriminant ability. The data vector spanned by the selected features is finally used as the input of the next layer. Finally, we perform a classification or regression task on the final representation obtained at the output of the final layer. The work is not intended to provide a novel shallow manifold learning method, rather it explores the use of a deep architecture that integrates manifold learning and feature selection.

Manifold learning techniques aim to project input data into another space where both the local neighborhood structure of the original samples and the global structure information of the observed samples are preserved. Graph-based manifold learning methods are examples of such cases that use the affinity graph to treat the data samples based on the relation between them. During the last years, different linear and nonlinear techniques, each with a specific objective function have been proposed.

Locality preserving projection (LPP) [15], Local Discriminant Embedding (LDE) [14], supervised locality preserving projection (SLPP) [51] and enhanced local discriminant embedding (ELDE) [53] are examples of linear embedding methods. The main advantage of these linear techniques over nonlinear ones (such as Locally linear embedding (LLE) [17] and Laplacian eigenmaps (LE) [16]) is that the former provide an explicit mapping function that allows the projection of out-of-sample data.

More recently, others supervised and semi-supervised manifold learning techniques have been developed for the purpose to capture both the global structure information and the neighborhood relationship of the observed samples. In [18], the authors present the discriminative low-rank preserving projection (DLRPP) algorithm, an adaptive graph-based supervised feature extraction method that fuses information from both the local manifold and the global structure of the data. In [19], the authors report a semi-supervised approach, called structured optimal graph based sparse feature extraction (SOGSFE) method, where sparse representation, label propagation, and discriminant projection are integrated into a unified framework.

It is important to stress that most of the above manifold learning methods can be fused in our scheme in order to obtain a deep-variant approach.

In order to validate our proposed framework, we have considered two different computer vision problems: face beauty prediction and face recognition.

Automatic facial beauty prediction is an emerging visual recognition problem which involve both classification and regression tasks. Previous attempts

to learn a standard to assess facial attractiveness consistent with human perception reveal the complexity of this problem especially when the amount of data used is limited. Common approaches include image feature descriptors such as geometric features [11, 12, 13, 20, 21], apparent features [22, 23] and recently deep features. This problem has been also approached using different manifold-learning-based methods such as LDA[24], LDE[14], among others.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we review the basic behind both the LDE algorithm and the Fisher feature selection method that represent the core of our proposed framework. The proposed algorithm details are reported in section 3. Section 4 describes the face databases and face descriptors used in this work. Experimental setup and results are disclosed in Section 5 and Section 6 respectively. We conclude this work in Section 7.

Table 1: Description of the main notations used in this paper.

Notation	Description
N	Number of images or samples
C	Number of classes
L	Number of layers
m	Number of least relevant features
\mathbf{x}	Vectorized image or feature vector $\in \mathbb{R}^D$
D	Dimension of the original data sample \mathbf{x}
d	Dimension of the projection space $d \leq D$
S_r	Fisher score of the r th feature
\mathbf{X}	Matrix of the original samples $\in \mathbb{R}^{D \times N}$
\mathbf{Z}	Matrix of the projected images or samples $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times N}$
\mathbf{y}	Vector of real scores $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^N$
\mathbf{A}	Projection matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ or $\mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$
\mathbf{w}	Ridge Regression model $\in \mathbb{R}^d$
\mathbf{W}	Graph similarity matrix $\in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$
\mathbf{L}	Laplacian matrix $\in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$
\mathbf{I}	Identity matrix
α, β	regularization parameters

2. Related work

In this section, we first review the linear method Local Discriminant Embedding (LDE), we then present the Fisher scoring method. In this paper, capital bold letters represent matrices and small bold letters represent vectors. Table 1 presents the main notations used in this paper.

In literature, one can find many works that provide graph-based techniques for metric learning and feature extractions [3, 4]. In [4], the authors designed a Dimensionality Reduction model based on an intraclass hypergraph, an interclass hypergraph, a supervised locality graph, and a weighted neighborhood margin to improve the compactness of the intraclass samples and the separability of the interclass samples. An optimal projection matrix can be achieved to extract the low-dimensional embedding features of hyperspectral images.

2.1. Local Discriminant Embedding

Local Discriminant Embedding [14] is a supervised linear embedding method that exploits local neighborhood and class relations of data to learn a discriminant embedding for the data. The main goal is to simultaneously maximize the local margin between heterogeneous samples and minimize the margin between homogeneous ones. This embedding method has proven to achieve good discriminating performance, due mainly to its ability to integrate the information of neighbors and class relations between data samples [25, 26, 27].

In order to alienate the sub-manifold of each class from one another and derive the linear embedding for subsequent classification tasks, LDE requires the construction of two adjacency graphs: the within-class graph G_w (an intrinsic graph in which the edges are limited to link pairs belonging to the same class) and the between-class graph G_b (a penalty graph in which the edges can link pairs belonging to different classes).

Assume the data are given by $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times N}$ matrix, where N denotes the number of samples and D refers to sample dimension. For each data sample \mathbf{x}_i (i th column of \mathbf{X}), two subsets, $N_w(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $N_b(\mathbf{x}_i)$ are computed. $N_w(\mathbf{x}_i)$ contains the neighbors sharing the same label with \mathbf{x}_i , while $N_b(\mathbf{x}_i)$ contains the neighbors having different labels. These two subsets are defined by two nearest neighbor graphs: one for homogeneous samples \mathbf{G}_w (parameterized by K_1) and one for heterogeneous samples \mathbf{G}_b (parameterized by K_2). Each

of these graphs is characterized by its corresponding affinity matrix $\mathbf{W}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{W}_b \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, respectively.

The linear embedding is then described by a matrix transform $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times d}$ that maps the data in the original space into a low dimensional space (of dimension $d < D$) where both geometrical and discriminant structures are preserved.

Formally, the linear transformation \mathbf{A} is obtained by optimizing the following criterion:

$$\max_{\mathbf{A}} \text{trace} \left\{ \left(\mathbf{A}^T \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_w \mathbf{A} \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{A}^T \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_b \mathbf{A} \right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

where the symmetric matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_b = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{L}_b \mathbf{X}^T$ denotes the locality preserving between-class scatter matrix, and the symmetric matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_w = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{L}_w \mathbf{X}^T$ denotes the locality preserving within-class scatter matrix. \mathbf{L}_b and \mathbf{L}_w are the Laplacian matrices of the graphs \mathbf{W}_b and \mathbf{W}_w , respectively.

The above optimization problem has a closed form solution due to the quadratic form. The columns of the sought matrix \mathbf{A} are given by the generalized eigenvectors associated with the largest eigenvalues of the following equation:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}_b \mathbf{a} = \lambda \tilde{\mathbf{S}}_w \mathbf{a} \quad (2)$$

Algorithm 1 LDE projection

Input:

- $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times N}$ the data matrix (image features) and their class labels
- LDE parameters: K_1 (homogeneous neighbors), K_2 (heterogeneous neighbors), β (regularization parameter)

Output:

- Mapping matrix \mathbf{A}
- Projected data \mathbf{Z}

Process

- 1: Compute the mapping matrix \mathbf{A} by solving Eq. (2) ;
 - 2: Compute the LDE projection $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{X}$;
-

2.2. Feature selection

The main objective of feature selection is to determine the best subsets of features (or variables) for performing statistical analysis task or building a

machine learning model [28, 29, 30, 31]. In the context of supervised learning, feature selection methods can be categorized into two classes: filter-based and wrapper-based methods. Wrapper-based feature selection requires the definition of both a predictive model and a search algorithm to score feature subsets. The optimal subset is obtained by training and testing a specific classification model while maximizing the classification performance. This renders this approach more dependent on the specific classification algorithm.

Alternatively, filter-based feature selection assess the relevance of features by considering only the intrinsic characteristics of the data. In this case, a suitable ranking criterion is used to score the variables and low-scoring features are ignored in the classification phase. These techniques have proven to be more suited to deal with very high-dimensional datasets and are computationally efficient.

In the past decade, several criteria have been proposed for filter-based feature selection, such as mutual information [32], ReliefF [33], Laplacian score [34] and Fisher score [35]. A survey on feature selection can be found in [36].

In this work, we use Fisher scoring of the features in order to extract the most relevant and discriminative features of the LDE projected features vector. Fisher scoring uses class labels to identify features with best discriminant ability [35]. The data space spanned by the selected features is such that the distances between data points in different classes are as large as possible, while the distances between data points in the same class are as small as possible. Formally, let $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ denote the feature vector obtained from the LDE projection at a given layer. The Fisher score of the r th feature is given by:

$$S_r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^c n_i (\mu_r^i - \mu_r)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^c n_i (\sigma_r^i)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where n_i is the size of i th class, and μ_r^i and σ_r^i refer to the mean and variance of the r th feature of the i th class, respectively. μ_r refers to the global mean of the r th feature. In the above formula, the numerator quantifies the class separability (it should be high for relevant features) while the denominator (it should be very small for relevant features) quantifies the class compactness.

The output of the feature selection is a vector of real scores allowing the ranking of the features. From this obtained ordering, several feature subsets can be chosen by setting a cutoff for the selected features. In this work, we have adopted the threshold-based criterion.

3. Proposed scheme: Feature Selection Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding (FSCLDE)

The proposed scheme consists of a cascade deep structure given by a number of layers, where each layer processes its input by carrying out two operations.

First, we project the input data onto a low dimensional space using LDE algorithm (See Algorithm 1). This mapping step is crucial to enhance data discrimination, and consequently, a better representation of data.

Second, we perform Fisher scoring according to Eq. (3) in order to identify features with best discriminant ability. At this stage we remove a certain number m of less relevant features (See 2). The analysis of this parameter (See Section 6) reveals that the performance of the algorithm is not very sensitive to number of removed features. However, the cleaning process itself seems to be relevant for a better discrimination. This can be explained by the model prediction boosting process achieved by iterating local discriminant embedding projection and feature subset selection.

The output of each layer, ℓ , gives a data representation spanned by the selected features. Formally, this output is given by the following transformation

$$\mathbf{x}_\ell = \left(\prod_{j=1}^{\ell} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_j \right)^T \mathbf{x}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x} denotes the original input descriptor. $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_j = \text{RemoveCol}_m(\mathbf{A}_j)$ and m is the number of removed features (a predefined parameter). $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_j$ is generated from \mathbf{A}_j that is provided by the current layer LDE transformation. $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_j$ is simply obtained from \mathbf{A}_j by removing the m columns associated with the eliminated features. This is feasible since the m eliminated projected features correspond to the m projections axes (columns) in the transform matrix.

Thus, at each layer the number of columns of $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_j$ decreases by m . From Eq. (4), we can derive the expression of the global transform associated with the proposed architecture with L layers, which is given by

$$\mathbf{A}_g = \prod_{j=1}^L \hat{\mathbf{A}}_j \quad (5)$$

For an unseen image whose descriptor is \mathbf{x}_{test} , its projection by the learned model, \mathbf{z}_{test} , is given by

$$\mathbf{z}_{test} = \mathbf{A}_g^T \mathbf{x}_{test} \quad (6)$$

Algorithm 2 summarizes the different steps involved in this scheme. For a graphical illustration, we refer the reader to Fig. 1. Fig. 2 illustrates the processing tasks in each layer that are applied on each sample after the model is learned.

As it can be appreciated, the scheme, illustrated in Fig. 1, can deal with different kinds of data and different problems. For face beauty prediction (top of Fig. 1), the input of the first layer is a VGG-face descriptor (could be any other descriptor), while for face recognition problem the input consists of the full image vector. A brief discussion on face features is reported in Section 4.3.

Face beauty prediction

Face recognition

Figure 1: Illustration of the Feature Selection based Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding structure for both face beauty (Top) and face recognition (bottom) problems. At each layer, some of the features (red part) that are irrelevant for the discrimination tasks will be removed after using LDE. At last, we will get a low-dimensional representative vector of the original image.

Figure 2: Illustration of the processing tasks in each layer that are applied on each sample after the model is learned. The input data is projected onto a low-dimensional embedding space where feature selection is performed allowing to preserve only the most relevant features. The input is a vector in \mathbb{R}^d . The output of this layer is a vector in \mathbb{R}^{d-m} . This is used as the input of the next layer.

Algorithm 2 Feature Selection based Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding (FSCLDE)

Input:

- $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times N}$ the data matrix (image features) and their class labels
- L the number of layers
- m the number of removed features at each layer

Output:

- Global linear transform \mathbf{A}_g
- Transformed data $\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}_N) \in \mathbb{R}^{(D-L.m) \times N}$

Process:

For each layer $j = 1, \dots, L$

- 1: Based on the previous layer features, compute the current layer transform \mathbf{A}_j and the current projected data using Algorithm 1;
- 2: Perform Fisher scoring and ranking using Eq. (3) on these projected features;
- 3: Identify the m least relevant features and remove them. This provides the current layer features;
- 4: Generate $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_j$ by removing the corresponding m columns in the transform matrix \mathbf{A}_j ;

End For

- Compute the global transform \mathbf{A}_g using Eq. (5);
 - Compute the projection of the data using $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{A}_g^T \mathbf{X}$;
-

3.1. Computational Complexity

As stated before, the proposed algorithm allows to transform any linear method to a deep variant by cascading two complementary processes: feature extraction and feature selection.

Thus, the computational complexity of a given layer will be the sum of that associated with both feature extraction and feature selection. As a linear feature extraction method, the algorithm relies on the LDE technique whose computational complexity is $\mathcal{O}(d N^2 + d^3)$ since this technique involves a k -NN search and an eigen decomposition problem associated with a $d \times d$ matrix. d is the dimension of the input features (for the first layer it is equal to the dimension of the original space, D) and N is the number of the training samples. We emphasize that the LDE projection yields a new space whose maximum dimension is given by that of the current input.

As for feature selection, the computational cost of the adopted Fisher score is $\mathcal{O}(d N C)$. Here, d is the projected features (for the first layer, it is equal to D) and C is the number of classes.

From the above analysis, we can easily conclude that the computational complexity of the first layer is $\mathcal{O}(D N^2 + D^3 + D N C)$. In the second layer, the dimensionality of data will become $D - m$ where m denotes the number of eliminated features. Thus, the computational cost of the second layer will be $\mathcal{O}((D - m) N^2 + (D - m)^3 + (D - m) N C)$. If we have L layers, the total computational complexity of the proposed method will be bounded by $\mathcal{O}(L (D N^2 + D^3 + D N C))$.

4. Databases and descriptors

As stated previously, the proposed approach has been evaluated considering two different computer vision problems: face beauty prediction which involve both classification and regression tasks, and face recognition which is a classical classification problem. Building computational models for face beauty prediction in images is a field that is still in its infancy [37, 38, 39].

Below is a brief description of the different databases and face features.

4.1. Face beauty databases

- **M²B** [40] dataset consists of facial, dressing images and audio files of 1240 females. The images are rated with various scores in the interval [1, 10] and belong to two ethnic groups: westerners and easterners (620 individuals in each group).

- **SCUT-FBP** [41] dataset contains 500 different Asian female subjects with attractiveness ratings, all of which have been verified in terms of rating distribution, standard deviation, consistency, and self-consistency. The beauty rankings (scores) lie in the interval [1, 5] and are the result of averaging various ratings.
- **SCUT-FBP5500** [42] dataset contains 5500 frontal, unoccluded faces of people between 15 and 60 years old with neutral expression. It can be divided into four subsets with different races and gender, including 2000 Asian females (AF), 2000 Asian males (AM), 750 Caucasian females (CF) and 750 Caucasian males (CM). All the images are labeled with beauty scores ranging from [1, 5].

4.2. Face recognition databases

- **Yale-B** [43] contains 2414 face images of 28 individuals under various facial expressions or configurations. The image size is 192×168 pixels with an 8-bit gray scale. The images have been resized to 32×32 pixels in our experiments.
- **Georgia** [44] contains images of 50 people. All people in the database are represented by 15 color JPEG images with cluttered background taken at resolution 640×480 pixels. The images have been resized to 140×140 pixels in our work.
- **PF01** [45] contains the true-color face images of 103 people, 53 men and 50 women, representing 17 various images (1 normal face, 4 illumination variations, 8 pose variations, 4 expression variations) per person. There are three kinds of systematic variations, such as illumination, pose, and expression variations in the database. The images have been resized to 32×32 pixels in our experiments.

Figure 3: Some samples of face images from the different databases used for face beauty prediction and classification.

Figure 4: Some samples of face images from the different databases used for face recognition.

4.3. Face features

Extracting face features from images can be done in many ways. For instance, one can use hand-crafted features such as Local Binary Patterns, Gabor features, Histograms of Oriented Gradients, etc. However, recent studies have proved that extracting features using a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) can provide more than satisfactory results in computer vision [46], often improving methods using other types of features, even if they are used in a task which is not exactly the one the network was trained to accomplish. Therefore, we adopt this transfer learning approach for our study and use the VGG-face network [47] as fixed feature extractor. The VGG-face network was trained for face identification. This trained network

Table 2: Databases used for experiments.

	Face beauty prediction				Face recognition				
	M ² B ¹	SCUT-FBP ²	SCUT5500 ³				Yale-B ⁴	Georgia ⁵	PF01 ⁶
			AF	AM	CF	CM			
# of instances	1240	500	2000	2000	750	750	2414	750	1819
Descriptor size	4096	4096	4096				1024	19600	1024
# of classes	5	4	4				28	50	103

¹ <https://sites.google.com/site/vantam/beautysense>

² <http://www.hcii-lab.net/data/SCUT-FBP/>

³ <https://github.com/HCIILAB/SCUT-FBP5500-Database-Release>

⁴ <http://vismod.media.mit.edu/vismod/classes/mas622-00/datasets/>

⁵ http://www.anefian.com/research/face_reco.htm

⁶ <http://imlab.postech.ac.kr/databases.htm>

is available for Matlab¹.

5. Experimental setup

The proposed framework for data representation has been used in three different real-world applications: face beauty classification, face beauty regression and face recognition. As stated previously, all images in face beauty databases are labeled with continuous beauty scores that range from 1 to 10 for M²B database, and from 1 to 5 for the other databases. Therefore, in order to carry out face beauty classification we transformed the continuous labels to discrete ones. Four classes have been considered: class 1 refers to least attractive faces and class 4 to most attractive ones. Thus classes 2 and 3 contain all in between faces. The result of this discretization process is summarized in Table 4. The adopted discretization was motivated by two facts: (i) a large number of beauty classes is not consistent with the subjective human evaluation as it is shown in [42], and (ii) the defined four classes are almost coinciding with the scores adopted in [42].

According to our proposed scheme (See Fig. 1), three modules need learning: (i) LDE projection, (ii) feature subset selection, and (iii) classification

¹The network can be downloaded from <http://www.vlfeat.org/matconvnet/pretrained/>.

Table 3: The validation protocol adopted for each database

Dataset	Validation protocol	Train/test
SCUT	5 random splits	70% - 30%
SCUT5500, M ² B	5-fold Cross validation	80% - 20%
Yale, Georgia, PF01	5 random splits	50% - 50%

or regression model. All of these modules were learned using a given training/testing configuration according to Table 3.

Performance measures are averaged over these 10 splits. Any training part of data contains the original images descriptors and their associated continuous or discrete labels.

To predict continuous scores we performed a ridge regression (RR) method which has proven to overcome some of the problems of ordinary least square methods by imposing a penalty on the size of the coefficient. The ridge regression method builds a linear model (represented by the vector \mathbf{w}) by minimizing the following penalized residual sum of square errors,

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}} \{ \|\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 + \alpha \|\mathbf{w}\|_2^2 \}$$

where \mathbf{Z} is the matrix of training data images in the projected space, \mathbf{y} is the vector that contains the scores of all training images, and $\alpha \geq 0$ is a complexity parameter that controls the amount of shrinkage: the larger the value of α the greater the amount of shrinkage is. Thus, the coefficients become more robust to collinearity. The ℓ_2 regularization is very useful for reducing over-fitting. The closed-form solution for the regression model is given by:

$$\mathbf{w} = (\mathbf{Z} \mathbf{Z}^T + \alpha \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{y}$$

In order to predict the real score of an unseen test image, \mathbf{x}_i , we proceed as follows. First, its projection \mathbf{z}_i is computed using the transform of Algorithm 2. Second, its predicted score of beauty will be estimated using the following inner product:

$$\hat{y}_i = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{z}_i$$

The k -nearest neighbor can also be used as a predictor for the face beauty score of the test image \mathbf{z}_i . Specifically, the k -nearest neighbor prediction is

Table 4: Discretization of the continuous labels in the datasets M²B and SCUT. In both cases, we adopted four discrete classes, where Class 1 stands for the least attractive faces (lowest rates) and class 4 for the most attractive ones (highest scores).

Dataset	Score range	Class1	Class2	Class3	Class4
M ² B	[1, 10]	[1, 4)	[4, 6)	[6, 8)	[8, 10]
SCUT-FBP	[1.20, 4.89]	[1.20, 2)	[2, 3)	[3, 4)	[4, 4.89]
SCUT5500-AF	[1.02, 4.75]	[1.02, 2)	[2, 3)	[3, 4)	[4, 4.75]
SCUT5500-AM	[1.17, 4.70]	[1.17, 2)	[2, 3)	[3, 4)	[4, 4.70]
SCUT5500-CF	[1.33, 4.70]	[1.33, 2)	[2, 3)	[3, 4)	[4, 4.70]
SCUT5500-CM	[1.55, 4.55]	[1.55, 2)	[2, 3)	[3, 4)	[4, 4.55]

given by:

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{\mathbf{z}_j \in N_k(\mathbf{z}_i)} y_j$$

where $N_k(\mathbf{z}_i)$ is the neighborhood of a given sample \mathbf{z} defined by the k closet points x_i in the training sample.

For discrete classes, that are adopted in face beauty classification and face recognition problems, the discrete label prediction is performed in the projected space using the classic k -nearest neighbor classifier.

5.1. Performance measures

5.1.1. Classification

The classification tasks have been evaluated using the average classification accuracy over different training/test splits. In addition to the classic accuracy, we used the F1 measure and Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC). The MCC returns a score between -1 and +1. A value of +1 means a perfect prediction, 0 no better than random prediction and -1 means total disagreement between prediction and observation.

For a binary classification problem, these are defined as follows. Based on the ground-truth and estimated labels, all tested images are grouped into four categories: True positive (TP), True negative (TN), False positive (FP), and False negative (FN). TP denotes the number of tested images that are correctly classified in the positive class.

The $F1$ measure is given by:

$$F_1 = 2 \frac{RP}{R + P} \quad (7)$$

where R and P denote the Recall and Precision, respectively. These are given by:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

The MCC is given by:

$$MCC = \frac{TP \cdot TN - FP \cdot FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (8)$$

For a multi-class classification problem (our case), each class can be regarded as "positive" and all other classes are considered as "negative". Thus, before computing the $F1$ measure, the global TP , TN , FP , and FN over all classes. A similar trick is done with MCC.

We also use Cohen's kappa². This measures the agreement between two methods that each classifies N items into C mutually exclusive categories.

$$Kappa = \frac{p_o - p_e}{1 - p_e} \quad (9)$$

where p_o is the relative observed agreement among methods (identical to accuracy), and p_e is the hypothetical probability of chance agreement, using the observed data to calculate the probabilities of each observer randomly seeing each category. If the methods are in complete agreement then $Kappa = 1$. If there is no agreement among the methods other than what would be expected by chance then the statistic is zero.

5.1.2. Score prediction

For a quantitative evaluation of the estimated face beauty scores, we considered different metrics such as the mean absolute error (MAE), the

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cohen's_kappa

root mean square error (RMSE), the Pearson's correlation coefficient (PC) and the ϵ -error [48, 49]. A brief formulation of these measures is given below.

Let y_i be the ground truth score and f_i be the estimated score, the error is then given as $e_i = y_i - f_i$. Assuming that the error sample set is unbiased, the MAE and RMSE are calculated as:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |e_i|. \quad (10)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2} \quad (11)$$

where n denotes the number of tested images.

The Pearson's correlation coefficient measures the linear correlation between the ground truth and the estimated scores and is given by:

$$PC = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})(f_i - \bar{f})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - \bar{f})^2}}, \quad (12)$$

where \bar{f} and \bar{y} are the means of the estimated scores and the ground truth scores, respectively.

The PC is a number in the interval $[-1, 1]$. It measures to what extent the points (y_i, f_i) , with $i = 1, \dots, n$, fit in their regression line. A PC around 1 or -1 means that there is a high linear correlation. On the other hand, a PC around 0 means that there exists no linear correlation.

In our particular case, a PC as close as possible to 1 is desirable, since a perfect prediction would be one in which $f_i = y_i$, in other words, the pairs (y_i, f_i) lie on the line $y = x$. Finally, whenever the ground-truth data contain both the scores and their uncertainties, the ϵ -error of the prediction is generally used [50], and is given by:

$$\epsilon\text{-error} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - e^{-\frac{e_i^2}{2\sigma_i^2}} \right), \quad (13)$$

where σ_i is the standard deviation of the scores of all the raters of image i . This error lies in the interval $[0, 1)$. Unlike the MAE and the RMSE, the ϵ -

error takes into account the uncertainty of the rate given by the standard deviation.

6. Experimental results

6.1. Hyperparameter tuning

Unlike other deep-learning-based approaches, the performance of our proposed method can be optimized by adjusting only a few number of parameters. In fact, the scheme architecture depends on two main parameters: the number of layers and the number of removed features. The remaining parameters, namely K_1 , K_2 and β are intrinsic to the LDE module, and can be optimized separately for a given number of layers.

In order to seek the optimal number of layers, we analyzed the classification accuracy of different models built with different number of layers ranging from 1 to 10. For this task, we tested the performance of our scheme on the three face beauty databases. The obtained results are reported in Fig. 5. For most databases, the classification accuracy shows an increasing pattern with the number of layers usually leading to a saturation level. But, for some subsets of the database SCUT5500, for example, for the AM and CF subsets, the accuracy reaches a certain maximum for a given number of layers.

(a) M²B database

(b) SCUT-FBP and SCUT5500 databases

Figure 5: The behavior pattern of the classification accuracy as a function of the number of layers. The number of removed features was fixed to $m = 300$ for M²B and SCUT5500 datasets, while for SCUT-FBP m was fixed to the value 200.

Although the number of layers is the most important parameter of the proposed scheme, the recursive cleaning process achieved by subset feature selection process is crucial to reach a good performance. To study the effect

of this parameter on the final performance, we first perform a Fisher scoring and ranking of the features, and then considered to remove m less relevant feature starting from $m = 100$ to $m = 500$. For the VGG-face descriptor (of size 4096), these values of m correspond to removing around 2% to 12% of less relevant features. Results corresponding to this experiment are reported in Fig. 6. As it can be seen, for three subsets of the SCUT5500 database (AF, AM and CM), the accuracy shows no significant changes when varying the parameter m . It appears that removing only few less relevant feature at each layer is enough to achieve a good performance. For the CF subset, however, the accuracy shows a Gaussian-like pattern with a maximum for $m = 300$.

Figure 6: The accuracy as a function of the number of less relevant removed feature. The number of layers has been fixed to $L = 5$.

7. Discussion

In this section, we report the results achieved by our method in solving both face beauty classification/prediction and face recognition problems.

In order to validate our method in solving face beauty regression problem, we carried out different experiments using two regression models: ridge regression and 1-NN regression (See Section 5). We considered to learn regression models on different embedding space: the input space spanned by

Table 5: **Face beauty ridge Regression**: performance scores carry out by Ridge Regression models on different subsets of the SCUT5500 dataset. Three configurations have been considered: (i) learning RR model using FSCLDE projection on vgg-face data; (ii) learning RR model on LDE projection of vgg-face data (iii) learning RR model directly with the original data without any embedding projection.

Dataset	Descriptor	MAE ↓	RMS ↓	ϵ -error ↓	PC (%) ↑
SCUT5500-AF	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0566	0.0727	0.1317	86.06
	VGG-face+LDE	0.0630	0.0814	0.1537	82.17
	VGG-face	0.0687	0.0995	0.1711	76.06
SCUT5500-AM	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0555	0.0718	0.1190	83.81
	VGG-face+LDE	0.0609	0.0795	0.1407	79.94
	VGG-face	0.0644	0.0846	0.1511	78.43
SCUT5500-CF	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0556	0.0706	0.1179	87.13
	VGG-face+LDE	0.0610	0.0768	0.1346	84.45
	VGG-face	0.0591	0.0775	0.1286	84.50
SCUT5500-CM	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0511	0.0653	0.1080	85.14
	VGG-face+LDE	0.0569	0.0728	0.1307	80.94
	VGG-face	0.0542	0.0700	0.1223	82.90

VGG-face descriptors; the space spanned by the projected VGG-face descriptors using the classic LDE; and the space resulting from adopting our FSCLDE method.

Tables 5 and 6 report respectively the average of different measures achieved by the RR regression and 1-NN models over 5 different splits. In Table 5, we can appreciate that the proposed configuration achieved on average an improvement of the PC indicator of about 5% and 7% with respect to the other two configurations respectively. For 1-NN regression models (See Table 6), the improvement was about 11%.

For face beauty classification, we conducted an extensive comparison of our method with the following linear embedding models LDE [14], SLPP [51], LPP [26], LDA [24], ANMM [52], ELDE [53] and ICS [54]. Results are depicted in Table 7. The performance improvements of our method with respect to the original LDE algorithm were significant for many subsets of the databases considered. For SCUT5500 database, the performance of the FSCLDE algorithm is at least 10% greater than the LDE performance,

Table 6: **Face beauty 1-NN regression:** performance scores carry out by 1-NN regression models on different subsets of the SCUT5500 dataset. Thwo configurations have been considered: (i) learning 1-NN model using FSCLDE projection on VGG-face data; (ii) learning 1-NN model directly with the original data without any embedding projection.

Dataset	Descriptor	MAE ↓	RMS ↓	ϵ -error ↓	PC (%) ↑
SCUT5500-AF	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0820	0.1072	0.2245	74.88
	VGG-face	0.0923	0.1206	0.2610	63.09
SCUT5500-AM	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0728	0.1015	0.1818	65.19
	VGG-face	0.0863	0.1182	0.2248	59.29
SCUT5500-CF	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0786	0.1032	0.1996	76.52
	VGG-face	0.0825	0.1080	0.2133	70.71
SCUT5500-CM	VGG-face+FSCLDE	0.0690	0.0869	0.1753	74.92
	VGG-face	0.0752	0.0978	0.2003	68.71

except for the CM subset where the difference was not significant. For M²B database, the improvements are about 5-6%.

Since our method upgrades the LDE method to a deep variant, we also conducted an additional comparison of our proposed scheme to this algorithm using other statistics such as Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC), F1-score and Cohen’s Kappa. These three indicators are defined in section 5.1.1. Results are disclosed in Table 8. As it can be appreciated, the proposed algorithm provides better performance and statistics than the LDE algorithm.

According to the obtained results, we can see that by introducing the FSCLDE scheme which can be considered as a deep metric learning tool, the performance of beauty classification and regression is enhanced with respect to the classic metric learning.

Similarly, to address the classical face recognition problem, three public face databases have been considered. The classification accuracy (in %) achieved by our scheme are shown in Table 9. The proposed scheme performs favorably on two databases (Georgia and PF01) with improvements around 2-4% with respect to the original LDE algorithm.

Table 7: **Face beauty classification**: recognition rate (%) achieved by a 1-NN classifier over different embedding spaces on three face beauty datasets. The number of removed features was fixed to $m = 300$, and the number of layers to 5.

Method	M ² Be	M ² Bw	SCUT	SCUT5500			
				AF	AM	CF	CM
SLPP [51]	38.90	48.39	69.33	61.70	70.15	69.33	70.93
LPP [26]	38.06	46.45	68.56	58.35	67.30	60.80	66.27
LDA [24]	38.71	43.23	71.20	54.95	58.55	65.07	64.13
ANMM [52]	37.74	47.10	64.40	58.40	66.80	62.00	65.73
ICS [54]	39.35	46.45	68.32	67.90	73.10	69.07	70.13
ELDE [53]	41.61	51.61	73.12	58.85	69.00	67.87	68.40
LDE [14]	40.32	52.260	74.40	58.40	66.80	62.00	72.00
FSCLDE (Ours)	42.58	55.81	74.56	70.05	74.60	70.80	72.40

SLPP *Supervised Locality Preserving Projection*
LPP *Locality Preserving Projections*
LDA *Local Discriminant Analysis*
ANMM *Average Neighborhood Margin Maximization*
ICS *Inter-class sparsity based discriminative least square regression*
ELDE *Enhanced Local Discriminant Embedding*
LDE *Local Discriminant Embedding*
FSCLDE *Feature Selection Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding*

Table 8: **Face beauty classification:** MCC, F1-score and Cohen’s Kappa statistics comparing the classical LDE algorithm to our proposed scheme FSCLDE on the SCUT database. The number of removed features was fixed to $m = 300$, and the number of layers to 5.

Method	MCC			
	AF	AM	CF	CM
LDE	0.5320	0.5707	0.5200	0.5467
FSCLDE	0.5860	0.6267	0.5449	0.6071
Method	F1-Score			
	AF	AM	CF	CM
LDE	0.6490	0.6780	0.6400	0.6600
FSCLDE	0.6895	0.7200	0.6587	0.7053
Method	Cohen’s Kappa			
	AF	AM	CF	CM
LDE	0.4239	0.3417	0.4080	0.3664
FSCLDE	0.4768	0.3596	0.4318	0.4108

LDE Local Discriminant Embedding
FSCLDE Feature Selection Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding

Table 9: **Face recognition:** classification rates (%) achieved by a 1-NN classifier over different embedding spaces on different databases. The number of layers and the number of removed features were optimized for each dataset.

Method	Yale-B	Georgia	PF01
SLPP [51]	96.67	72.40	84.37
LPP [26]	95.86	60.40	67.70
LDA [24]	31.27	64.50	75.61
ANMM [52]	88.34	56.05	58.77
ICS [54]	97.28	77.30	81.83
ELDE [53]	94.47	68.00	76.00
LDE [14]	97.47	78.45	82.15
FSCLDE (The proposed approach)	97.93	80.25	85.55

SLPP Supervised Locality Preserving Projection
LPP Locality Preserving Projections
LDA Local Discriminant Analysis
ANMM Average Neighborhood Margin Maximization
ICS Inter-class sparsity based discriminative least square regression
ELDE Enhanced Local Discriminant Embedding
LDE Local Discriminant Embedding
FSCLDE Feature Selection Cascade Local Discriminant Embedding

8. Conclusion

In this work, we have developed a simple deep learning computer vision approach that is not based on artificial neural networks. The introduced framework overcomes some of the drawbacks characterizing most Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). In fact, training CNN is known to require a large amount of data due mainly to the huge number of learnable parameters to estimate. This makes CNN more computationally expensive, and graphical processing units (GPUs) for model training are usually required.

Unlike CNNs, the proposed scheme requires the definition of a very limited number of parameters, and consequently, the learning process can be handled with a small amount of data. In the proposed framework, The learning is performed layer-by-layer. Indeed, our method is a deep manifold-learning approach strategy that relies on a cascade-based architecture where the network is split into different layers. At each layer, we perform two operations. First, we project the input data onto a low dimensional space using the supervised Local Discriminant Embedding (LDE) algorithm. Second, we perform a Fisher scoring of the obtained features in order to identify and retain those with best discriminant ability. The data vector spanned by the selected features is finally used as the input of the next layer. Finally, we perform classification or regression tasks on the final representation obtained at the output of the final layer. The proposed approach is generic in the sense that it can be used any manifold learning method in order to learn the mapping of a given layer.

To validate our method, we have considered two different computer vision problems: face beauty prediction (both discrete classification and regression) and face recognition. Experiments conducted on different databases show that our method performs favorably compared to other embedding approaches.

With regards to the face beauty prediction, we can see that by introducing the FSCLDE scheme which can be considered as a deep metric learning tool, the classification and regression performance is enhanced with respect to the use of the classic metric learning.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Fulin Luo, Hong Huang, Yule Duan, Jiamin Liu and Yinghua Liao. *Local Geometric Structure Feature for Dimensionality Reduction of Hyperspectral Imagery Remote Sens.* 2017, 9(8), 790, Aug 2017.
- [2] F. Luo, B. Du, L. Zhang, L. Zhang and D. Tao. *Feature Learning Using Spatial-Spectral Hypergraph Discriminant Analysis for Hyperspectral Image* *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 2406-2419, July 2019.
- [3] F. Luo and L. Zhang and X. Zhou and T. Guo and Y. Cheng and T. Yin. *Sparse-Adaptive Hypergraph Discriminant Analysis for Hyperspectral Image Classification.* *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 2019.
- [4] F. Luo, L. Zhang, B. Du and L. Zhang. *Dimensionality Reduction With Enhanced Hybrid-Graph Discriminant Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification.* *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 2019.
- [5] Christian Szegedy, Vincent Vanhoucke, Sergey Ioffe, Jonathon Shlens, Zbigniew Wojna: Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision. *CoRR abs/1512.00567* (2015)
- [6] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton. Deep learning. *Nature*, 251:436–444, 2015.
- [7] J. Gu, Z. Wang, J. Kuen, L. Ma, A. Shahroudy, B. Shuai, T. Liu, X. Wang, G. Wang, J. Cai, and T. Chen. Recent advances in convolutional neural networks. *Pattern Recognition*, 77:354–377, 2018.
- [8] Lei Li, Zhaoqiang Xia, Abdenour Hadid, Xiaoyue Jiang, Haixi Zhang, and Xiaoyi Feng. Replayed video attack detection based on motion blur analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, PP, 01 2019.
- [9] Zhi-Hua Zhou and Ji Feng. Deep forest: Towards an alternative to deep neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.08835*, 2017.

- [10] Wei Shen, Yilu Guo, Yan Wang, Kai Zhao, Bo Wang, and Alan Yuille. Deep regression forests for age estimation. In *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 2304–2313. IEEE, 2018.
- [11] Amit Kagian, Gideon Dror, Tommer Leyvand, Isaac Meilijson, Daniel Cohen-Or, and Eytan Ruppin. A machine learning predictor of facial attractiveness revealing human-like psychophysical biases. *Vision research*, 48(2):235–243, 2008.
- [12] Pamela M Pallett, Stephen Link, and Kang Lee. New “golden” ratios for facial beauty. *Vision research*, 50(2):149–154, 2010.
- [13] H İrem Türkmen, Zeyneb Kurt, and M Elif Karsligil. Global feature based female facial beauty decision system. In *Signal Processing Conference, 2007 15th European*, pages 1945–1949. IEEE, 2007.
- [14] Hwann-Tzong Chen, Huang-Wei Chang, and Tyng-Luh Liu. Local discriminant embedding and its variants. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2005. CVPR 2005. IEEE Computer Society Conference on*, volume 2, pages 846–853. IEEE, 2005.
- [15] X. He, P. Niyogi Locality preserving projections *Advances in neural information processing systems* 16, MIT Press (2004), pp. 153-160
- [16] M. Belkin, P. Niyogi Laplacian eigenmaps for dimensionality reduction and data representation *Neural Computation*, 15 (6) (2003), pp. 1373-1396
- [17] S. Roweis, L. Saul Nonlinear dimensionality reduction by locally linear embedding *Science*, 290 (5500) (2000), pp. 2323-2326
- [18] Zhonghua Liu, Jingjing Wang, Gang Liu, Lin Zhang, Discriminative low-rank preserving projection for dimensionality reduction, *Applied Soft Computing*, Volume 85, 2019, 105768,
- [19] Zhonghua Liu, Zhihui Lai, Weihua Ou, Kaibing Zhang, Ruijuan Zheng, Structured optimal graph based sparse feature extraction for semi-supervised learning, *Signal Processing*, Volume 170, 2020, 107456

- [20] Christopher D Green. All that glitters: A review of psychological research on the aesthetics of the golden section. *Perception*, 24(8):937–968, 1995.
- [21] Junying Gan, Lichen Li, Yikui Zhai, and Yinhua Liu. Deep self-taught learning for facial beauty prediction. *Neurocomputing*, 144:295–303, 2014.
- [22] Yael Eisenbal, Gideon Dror, and Eytan Ruppin. Facial attractiveness: Beauty and the machine. *Neural Computation*, 18(1):119–142, 2006.
- [23] Douglas Gray, Kai Yu, Wei Xu, and Yihong Gong. Predicting facial beauty without landmarks. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 434–447. Springer, 2010.
- [24] Peter N Belhumeur, João P Hespanha, and David J Kriegman. Eigenfaces vs. fisherfaces: Recognition using class specific linear projection. Technical report, Yale University New Haven United States, 1997.
- [25] Alireza Bosaghzadeh, Abdelmalik Moujahid, and Fadi Dornaika. Parameterless local discriminant embedding. *Neural Processing Letters*, 38(1):53–67, Aug 2013.
- [26] Xiaofei He and Partha Niyogi. Locality preserving projections. In *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pages 153–160, 2004.
- [27] Lishan Qiao, Songcan Chen, and Xiaoyang Tan. Sparsity preserving projections with applications to face recognition. *Pattern Recognition*, 43(1):331–341, 2010.
- [28] Z. Peng, P. Gurram, H. Kwon, and W. Yin. Sparse kernel learning-based feature selection for anomaly detection. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 51(3):1698–1716, July 2015.
- [29] Giorgio Roffo and Simone Melzi. Features selection via eigenvector centrality. *Proceedings of New Frontiers in Mining Complex Patterns (NFMCP 2016)(Oct 2016)*, 2016.
- [30] Yi Yang, Heng Tao Shen, Zhigang Ma, Zi Huang, and Xiaofang Zhou. $l_2, 1$ -norm regularized discriminative feature selection for unsupervised learning. In *IJCAI proceedings-international joint conference on artificial intelligence*, volume 22, page 1589, 2011.

- [31] Giorgio Roffo, Simone Melzi, Umberto Castellani, and Alessandro Vinciarelli. Infinite latent feature selection: A probabilistic latent graph-based ranking approach. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2017.
- [32] Daphne Koller and Mehran Sahami. Toward optimal feature selection. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on International Conference on Machine Learning*, ICML'96, pages 284–292, San Francisco, CA, USA, 1996. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc.
- [33] Marko Robnik-Šikonja and Igor Kononenko. Theoretical and empirical analysis of relieff and rrelieff. *Machine Learning*, 53(1):23–69, Oct 2003.
- [34] Xiaofei He, Deng Cai, and Partha Niyogi. Laplacian score for feature selection. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, NIPS'05, pages 507–514, Cambridge, MA, USA, 2005. MIT Press.
- [35] Quanquan Gu, Zhenhui Li, and Jiawei Han. Generalized fisher score for feature selection. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, UAI'11, pages 266–273, Arlington, Virginia, United States, 2011. AUAI Press.
- [36] Girish Chandrashekar and Ferat Sahin. A survey on feature selection methods. *Comput. Electr. Eng.*, 40(1):16–28, January 2014.
- [37] Aldo Laurentini and Andrea Bottino. Computer analysis of face beauty: A survey. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 125:184–199, 2014.
- [38] D. Zhang, F. Chen, and Y. Xu. *Computer models for facial beauty analysis*. Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2016.
- [39] Shu Liu, Bo Li, Yangyu Fan, Zhe Guo, and Ashok Samal. Facial attractiveness computation by label distribution learning with deep cnn and geometric features. *2017 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*, pages 1344–1349, 2017.
- [40] Tam V. Nguyen, Si Liu, Bingbing Ni, Jun Tan, Yong Rui, and Shuicheng Yan. Sense beauty via face, dressing, and/or voice. In *Proceedings of*

the 20th ACM International Conference on Multimedia, MM '12, pages 239–248, New York, NY, USA, 2012. ACM.

- [41] Duorui Xie, Lingyu Liang, Lianwen Jin, Jie Xu, and Mengru Li. SCUT-FBP: A benchmark dataset for facial beauty perception. *CoRR*, abs/1511.02459, 2015.
- [42] Lingyu Liang, LuoJun Lin, Lianwen Jin, Duorui Xie, and Mengru Li. Scut-fbp5500: A diverse benchmark dataset for multi-paradigm facial beauty prediction. 2018.
- [43] A. S. Georghiadis, P. N. Belhumeur, and D. J. Kriegman. From few to many: illumination cone models for face recognition under variable lighting and pose. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 23(6):643–660, June 2001.
- [44] Ara V. Nefian. Georgia tech face database. 1999.
- [45] H. Je, S. Kim, B. Jun, D. Kim, H. Kim, J. Sung, and S. Bang. Asian face image database pf01. *Intelligent Multimedia Lab, Dept. of CSE, POSTECH*, 2001.
- [46] Ali Sharif Razavian, Hossein Azizpour, Josephine Sullivan, and Stefan Carlsson. Cnn features off-the-shelf: an astounding baseline for recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition workshops*, pages 806–813, 2014.
- [47] Omkar M Parkhi, Andrea Vedaldi, Andrew Zisserman, et al. Deep face recognition. In *BMVC*, volume 1, page 6, 2015.
- [48] K. Willmott, CJ; Matsuura. Advantages of the mean absolute error (mae) over the root mean square error (rmse) in assessing average model performance. *Climate Research*, 30:79–82, 2005.
- [49] Joseph Lee Rodgers and W. Alan Nicewander. Thirteen ways to look at the correlation coefficient. *The American Statistician*, 42(1):59–66, 1988.
- [50] Rasmus Rothe, Radu Timofte, and Luc Van Gool. Deep expectation of real and apparent age from a single image without facial landmarks. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 126(2):144–157, Apr 2018.

- [51] Zhonglong Zheng, Fan Yang, Wenan Tan, Jiong Jia, and Jie Yang. Gabor feature-based face recognition using supervised locality preserving projection. *Signal Processing*, 87(10):2473–2483, 2007.
- [52] Xiao-Ming Liu, Zhao-Hui Wang, and Zhi-Lin Feng. Average neighborhood margin maximization projection with smooth regularization for face recognition. In *Machine Learning and Cybernetics, 2008 International Conference on*, volume 1, pages 401–406. IEEE, 2008.
- [53] Fadi Dornaika and Alireza Bosaghzadeh. Exponential local discriminant embedding and its application to face recognition. *IEEE transactions on cybernetics*, 43(3):921–934, 2013.
- [54] Jie Wen, Yong Xu, Zuoyong Li, Zhongli Ma, and Yuanrong Xu. Inter-class sparsity based discriminative least square regression. *Neural Networks*, 102:36–47, 2018.